

A Study on Customer Satisfaction Towards Allen Solly Apparels in Ahmedabad City

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the level of customer satisfaction with Allen Solly apparels in Ahmedabad city with the aim to provide some valuable insights of components influencing customer preferences in the competitive apparel market. The used quantitative research method to gather the data from a diverse sample of Allen Solly customers in Ahmedabad. The research objectives includes evaluating customer satisfaction, identifying factors influencing purchasing decisions, assessing how the customer service is effective, and understanding viewpoint of product quality and brand name. The survey instruments includes Likert - scale questions to collect quantitative aspects of customer satisfaction. The findings of this research concludes the strengths and weaknesses of Allen Solly in Ahmedabad City. Moreover, the research aims to provide implementable suggestions for the company to improve customer satisfaction, loyalty, and competitiveness in the evolving retail environment. This study serves as an essential reference for researchers, professionals, and shareholders interested in understanding consumer behaviour and improving strategies

INTRODUCTION

The retail industry of India is one of the fastest developing industry in the world (Vidani, 2015). India is ranked as 5th biggest favoured retail objective (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). It is expected that India will become the world's 3rd largest consumer economy, reaching Rs.27.95 lakh crores (i.e. US \$ 400 billion) by 2025 (Vidani, 2015). The Indian government has implied changes withdrawn in Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in retail industry (Vidani, 2015). The public authority has countersigned 51% FDI in multi-brand retail and 100% in single-brand retail (Vidani, 2015) (Solanki & Vidani, 2016) (Chandrakhanthan J.,2022).

The zest among global luxury brand to capture Indian luxury market portrays that India's luxury market is on strong growth path (Vidani, 2016) (Vidani, 2016) (Arpit, 2023).

In year 1744, William Hollin and co. ltd established a brand-named Allen Solly (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017) (Vidani J. N., 2016) (Vidani & Singh, 2017). Later in 90s Madura Fashion bought the brand, which was then acquired by Aditya Birla Fashion and Lifestyle (Niyati & Vidani, 2016) (Pradhan, Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016) (Modi, Harkani, Radadiya, & Vidani, 2016). Along with that 207 new stores were inaugurate in India; Allen Solly also poised to expand in international market as well (Vidani, 2016) (Vidani & Pathak, 2016) (Pathak & Vidani, 2016) (Arpit, 2023).

Talking about the brand Allen Solly, it came to India in 1993, introducing an entirely new consumer class (Vidani, 2016) (Sukhanandi, Tank, & Vidani, 2018)(Singh, Vidani, & Nagoria, 2016)(Mala, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016). Allen Solly introduced itself with a hit idea of "Friday Dressing" (Dhere, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016)(Singh & Vidani, 2016). Also, the company formed their tagline to specify the brand's new trend (Vidani & Plaha, 2016)(Solanki & Vidani, 2016). Later on, Allen Solly became the 1st Indian brand to introduced work fashion for ladies (Vidani, 2016)(Vidani, Chack, & Rathod, 2017) (Dr. A. Helda Mary, 2022).

We frequently hear the term customer satisfaction in marketing (Vidani & Plaha, 2017) (Vidani, Chack, & Rathod, 2017) (Vidani, 2018). It means how products or services meets or surpasses the customer's expectation (Biharani & Vidani, 2018) (Vidani, 2018)(Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018). Every company's main goal should be their customers' satisfaction (Vasveliyya & Vidani, 2019) (Sachaniya, Vora, & Vidani, 2019). The factors that affect a customer's satisfaction includes department wise capacity supplier, technological aspects and various factors (Vidani, 2019) (Vidani, Jacob, & Patel, 2019) (Arpit, 2023).

Customer experience is one of the crucial factors in today's competitive business environment (Vidani J. N., 2018) (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020). A positive customer experience may lead to increase in customer's satisfaction level, loyalty, and purchase intention (Vidani J. N., 2018).

Nowadays, buyers have more alternative options than before in this digital world (Vidani & Das, 2021)(Rathod, Meghrajani, & Vidani, 2022) (Vidani, Meghrajani, & Siddarth, 2023). Before making any purchase decision, customers are likely to compare the cost and features of other products as well as read the customer reviews (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020) (Vidani & Das, 2021) (Vidani J. N.,

2022) (Saxena & Vidani, 2023). Therefore, every business should concentrate on offering superior customer experience in order to draw in and keep customers (Arpit, 2023) (Vidani, Das, Meghrajani, & Singh, 2023).

Current Trends

It is expected that by 2026 the fashion retail industry in India is expected to grow to \$150 billion (Vidani, Das, Meghrajani, & Singh, 2023) (Vidani, Das, Meghrajani, & Chaudasi, 2023). The rapid growth of online fashion retail market is expected to account for over 40% of the total fashion retail market by 2026 (Rathod, Meghrajani, & Vidani, 2022) (Bansal, Pophalkar, & Vidani, 2023) (Arpit, 2023).

Market Share (Global & India)

One of the top fashion labels in India, Allen Solly has more than 500 retail locations (Vidani & Das, 2021) (Vidani J. N., 2022) (Chaudhary, Patel, & Vidani, 2023). The business provides a huge selection of clothing, accessories, and home furnishings (Gupta G., 2021) (Patel, Chaudhary, & Vidani, 2023) (Arpit, 2023).

Scope of Industry Growth in this Sector

Over the five years, it is expected that Indian fashion retail will expand at a CAGR of 10% (Sharma & Vidani, 2023). Increased disposable incomes, urbanization, and the growing acceptance of internet shopping will be the main drivers of the rise (Sharma & Vidani, 2023) (Arpit, 2023).

Objective of the Research

1. To identify the factors that affects satisfaction level of customers towards Allen Solly apparels.
2. To know the factors on the basis of which customers' makes their purchase decision.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Ritu Narang (2006) conducted a research study to on title "A study on Branded Men's wear" Sonapat city to de determine purchase behaviour of buyers of men's wear and also to study the advertisement effects purchase decision of customers. The research type us it was our exploratory research type and it in the end it was concluded that buyers visit the showrooms of branded garments for shopping

DR. A. Helda Mary, Mohammed Lughman NK (2002) conducted a study on "Effectiveness of advertisement on Allen Solly apparels with special reference to Coimbatore City. The factors considered during this study were name, Product category, Preference for cloth type, advertisement trends, fashion trends, Effect of discount, & offer. There is total 120 responses collected & evaluated. After the analysis it was found the discount offers & current advertisement trend play's a decisive role within apparel shopping beside purchase value. The study concluded that consumer behaviour towards apparel brands not only depends other impact factors also was most preferred- on brand but other impacts factors also was most preferred.

Dr. Prasad V.K. Satya (2014) conducted a research study on "Perception of consumers towards apparels brands and factors influencing the preference of apparels brands". The study used qualitative as well as quantitative research

method to collect the data. The sample size was 100 respondents, and they were the college going students who preferred to wear branded clothes. The research concluded that there are five major factors which affects purchase decision of customers, those five factors are namely Product attribute, Facilities offered, store attributes, brand loyalty and policy.

Prasath Kumar A., Jagannathan. K (2022) conducted a study which talked about "Import of store Interior Design in Young Consumer attention at Allen Solly Junior. The study focused on how interior store design attract customer. After the investigation/observation they found that there is a connection between the youthful client for inside store and visual promotion. At the end they concluded that a company or a store should focus on the interior design to attract customer/people.

S.Pathak and A.Tripathi (2009) made a study titled "Customer Shopping behaviour among Modern Retail Formats: A study of Delhi and NCR." It was exploratory research with the objective to find out the factors influencing customer's decision among the modern retail formats and to evaluate the comparative strength of these factors in purchasing decisions of customers. It was concluded that retailers at times overlook the schemes and offerings expected by buyers and tried to impose their own offerings on buyers which causes dissatisfaction.

Hypothesis Testing

- H1: There is significant association between age of respondent and visits to the Allen Solly store.
- H2: There is significant association between age of respondent and overall ambiance and cleanliness of Allen Solly stores.
- H3: There is significant association between age of respondent and availability of various clothing options in Allen Solly stores.
- H4: There is significant association between age of respondent and staff's assistance and knowledge about Allen Solly products.
- H5: There is significant association between age of respondent and quality of Allen Solly apparels.
- H6: There is significant association between age of respondent and variety of designs and styles offered by Allen Solly
- H7: There is significant association between age of respondent and pricing of Allen Solly apparel in comparison to the quality.
- H8: There is significant association between age of respondent and taking advantage of Allen Solly's discounts and promotions
- H9: There is significant association between age of respondent and overall satisfaction with shopping experience at Allen Solly stores.

METHODOLOGY

- Type of research - Primary research
- Research design - Descriptive research design
- Participants - People living in Ahmedabad city
- Area of research - Ahmedabad
- No. of respondents - 131
- Sampling method - Non - probability- Convenient sampling
- Data collection method - Questionnaire - Google form
- Analysis collected data - MS Excel and SPSS

RESULT

Data Analysis

Demographic summary

1. AGE

- 64.9% of the population falls under the age group of 18-24 years.
- 9.9% falls under the age group of 25-34 years.
- 12.2% falls under the age group of 35-44 years.
- 6.1% falls under the age group of 44-54 years.
- 6.9% are of 55 years and above.

2. GENDER

The sample is made up of 131 participants out of which 58% are males and 42% are females.

Cronbach Alpha

Table. 1 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.902	11

Source: SPSS Software

The data is reliable because the alpha value is 0.902 which is more than 0.07.

Hypotheses Testing

- Chi-Square Analysis

H1: There is significant association between age of respondent and visits to the Allen Solly store.

Age * Visits Consideration

Table 2. Crosstab: Age & Visits Consideration

Count		How often do you visit Allen Solly stores in Ahmedabad?					Total
		very often	often	occasionally	rarely	never	
AGE	18-24	12	8	22	22	21	85
	25-34	4	2	3	2	2	13
	35-44	3	5	2	6	0	16
	45-54	3	0	2	1	2	8
	55 and above	1	1	3	3	1	9
Total		23	16	32	34	26	131

Source: SPSS Software

Table 3. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.497 ^a	16	.296
Likelihood Ratio	20.912	16	.182
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.054	1	.152
N of Valid Cases	131		

Source: SPSS Software

a. 20 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .98

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H1. This shows that there is no relationship between age of respondent and visits consideration for Allen Solly stores

H2: There is significant association between age of respondent and overall ambiance and cleanliness of Allen Solly stores.

Age * overall ambiance and cleanliness Consideration

Table 4. Crosstab: Age & Overall Ambiance and Cleanliness Consideration

Count		How would you rate the overall ambiance and cleanliness of Allen Solly stores in Ahmedabad?					Total
		Excellent	very good	good	fair	poor	
AGE	18-24	24	25	28	4	4	85
	25-34	3	3	5	2	0	13
	35-44	4	5	3	4	0	16
	45-54	2	3	0	2	1	8
	55 and above	1	1	2	5	0	9
Total		34	37	38	17	5	131

Table 5. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	29.268 ^a	16	.022
Likelihood Ratio	28.133	16	.030
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.076	1	.024
N of Valid Cases	131		

Source: SPSS Software

a. 21 cells (84.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .31.

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H2. This shows that there is no relationship between age of respondent and overall ambiance and cleanliness consideration for Allen Solly stores.

H3: There is significant association between age of respondent and availability of various clothing options in Allen Solly stores.

Age * availability of various clothing options in Allen Solly stores considerations.

Table 6. Crosstab: Age & Availability of Various Clothing Options in Allen Solly Stores Considerations

Count		Please rate the availability of various clothing options in Allen Solly stores.					Total
		very satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	unsatisfied	very unsatisfied	
AGE	18-24	25	30	24	3	3	85
	25-34	3	3	7	0	0	13
	35-44	5	5	4	1	1	16
	45-54	3	2	1	1	1	8
	55 and above	1	2	2	4	0	9
Total		37	42	38	9	5	131

Source: SPSS Software

Table 7. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	29.996 ^a	16	.018
Likelihood Ratio	20.996	16	.179
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.743	1	.053
N of Valid Cases	131		

Source: SPSS Software

a. 20 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .31

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H3. This shows that there is no relationship between age of respondent and availability of various

cl H4: There is significant association between age of respondent and knowledge about Allen Solly products

Age * the staff's assistance and knowledge about Allen Solly products

Table 8. Crosstab: Age & the Staff's Assistance and Knowledge About Allen Solly Products

Crosstab

Count

		How satisfied are you with the staff's assistance and knowledge about Allen Solly products?					Total
		very satisfied	satisfied	Neutral	unsatisfied	very unsatisfied	
AGE	18-24	25	30	20	5	5	85
	25-34	5	6	2	0	0	13
	35-44	6	3	4	2	1	16
	45-54	3	2	1	1	1	8
	55 and above	2	1	5	1	0	9
Total		41	42	32	9	7	131

Source: SPSS Software

Table 9. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.036 ^a	16	.670
Likelihood Ratio	14.330	16	.574
Linear-by-Linear Association	.539	1	.463
N of Valid Cases	131		

Source: SPSS Software

a. 19 cells (76.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .43

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H4. This shows that there is no relationship between age of the staff's assistance and knowledge about Allen Solly products

H5: There is significant association between age of respondent and the quality of Allen Solly apparels

Age * the quality of Allen Solly apparels considerations

Table 10. Crosstab: Age & the Quality of Allen Solly Apparels Considerations
 Crosstab

Count		How satisfied are you with the quality of Allen Solly apparels?					Total
		very satisfied	satisfied	neutral	Unsatisfied	very unsatisfied	
AGE	18-24	25	32	18	5	5	85
	25-34	4	4	5	0	0	13
	35-44	7	5	2	1	1	16
	45-54	3	1	2	1	1	8
	55 and above	1	1	5	2	0	9
Total		40	43	32	9	7	131

Source: SPSS Software

Table 11. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	17.531 ^a	16	.352
Likelihood Ratio	18.254	16	.309
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.545	1	.214
N of Valid Cases	131		

Source: SPSS Software

a. 20 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .43

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H5. This shows that there is no relationship between age & the quality of Allen Solly apparels considerations

H6: There is significant association between age of respondent and styles offered by Allen Solly.

Age * the variety of designs and styles offered by Allen Solly.

Table 12. Crosstab: Age & the Variety of Designs and Styles Offered by Allen Solly
Crosstab

Count		Please rate your satisfaction with the variety of designs and styles offered by Allen Solly.					Total
		very satisfied	satisfied	neutral	Unsatisfied	very unsatisfied	
AGE	18-24	22	37	19	3	4	85
	25-34	2	4	5	2	0	13
	35-44	6	4	4	1	1	16
	45-54	4	1	1	1	1	8
	55 and above	3	1	2	3	0	9
Total		37	47	31	10	6	131

Source: SPSS Software

Table 13. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	22.488 ^a	16	.128
Likelihood Ratio	20.479	16	.199
Linear-by-Linear Association	.720	1	.396
N of Valid Cases	131		

Source: SPSS Software

a. 20 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .37

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H6. This shows that there is no relationship between age & the quality of Allen Solly apparels considerations

H7: There is significant association between ages of respondent and pricing of Allen Solly apparel in comparison to the quality

Age * pricing of Allen Solly apparel in comparison to the quality considerations.

Table 14. Crosstab: Age & Pricing of Allen Solly Apparel in Comparison to the Quality Considerations

Crosstab

Count		How do you perceive the pricing of Allen Solly apparel in comparison to the quality?					Total
		very reasonable	Reasonable	Neutral	expensive	very expensive	
AGE	18-24	16	25	24	12	8	85
	25-34	3	5	2	2	1	13
	35-44	3	7	2	3	1	16
	45-54	3	2	1	1	1	8
	55 and above	2	1	2	4	0	9
Total		27	40	31	22	11	131

Source: SPSS Software

Table 15. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.840 ^a	16	.755
Likelihood Ratio	11.618	16	.770
Linear-by-Linear Association	.012	1	.913
N of Valid Cases	131		

Source: SPSS Software

a. 20 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .67.

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H7. This shows that there is no relationship between age of respondent and visits consideration for Allen Solly stores.

H8: There is significant association between age of respondent and taking advantage of Allen Solly's discounts and promotions.

Age * taking advantage of Allen Solly's discounts and promotions considerations.

Table 16. Crosstab: Age & Taking Advantage of Allen Solly's Discounts and Promotions Considerations

Crosstab

Count		how often do you take advantage of Allen Solly's discounts and promotions?					Total
		very often	often	Occasionally	Rarely	never	
AGE	18-24	18	14	27	18	8	85
	25-34	3	2	6	1	1	13
	35-44	4	3	5	2	2	16
	45-54	4	1	0	1	2	8
	55 and above	2	0	3	3	1	9
Total		31	20	41	25	14	131

Source: SPSS Software

a. 19 cells (76.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .85

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H8. This shows that there is no relationship between age of respondent and visits consideration for Allen Solly stores

H9: There is significant association between ages of respondent and satisfied are you with your shopping experience at Allen Solly in Ahmedabad.

Age*satisfied are you with your shopping experience at Allen Solly in Ahmedabad considerations

Table 17. Crosstab: Age & Satisfied are you with Your Shopping Experience at Allen Solly in Ahmedabad Considerations

Crosstab

Count		Overall, how satisfied are you with your shopping experience at Allen Solly in Ahmedabad?					Total
		very satisfied	satisfied	neutral	Unsatisfied	very unsatisfied	
AGE	18-24	27	30	24	0	4	85
	25-34	5	4	4	0	0	13
	35-44	6	3	5	1	1	16
	45-54	4	0	2	1	1	8
	55 and above	2	1	5	1	0	9
Total		44	38	40	3	6	131

Source: SPSS Software

Table 18. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	20.622 ^a	16	.194
Likelihood Ratio	22.026	16	.142
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.689	1	.194
N of Valid Cases	131		

Source: SPSS Software

a. 21 cells (84.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H9. This shows that there is no relationship between age of respondent and visits consideration for Allen Solly stores

DISCUSSION

The focus of the research is to identify the factors that influence the purchase decisions of customers and their satisfaction level towards Allen Solly apparel in the city of Ahmedabad (Vidani, 2015) (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). The data for the research was collected through a questionnaire (Google Form) from a total of 131 respondents (Solanki & Vidani, 2016) (Vidani, 2016).

Demographic Overview:

The survey provides an overview of respondents' demographics, including age and gender (Solanki & Vidani, 2016) (Vidani, 2016). The majority of

respondents (64.9%) are between the ages of 18 and 24 (Pradhan, Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016) (Modi, Harkani, Radadiya, & Vidani, 2016). The sample is made up of 58% males and 42% females, which suggests that males are more likely to shop for Allen Solly apparel than females (Pradhan, Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016) (Modi, Harkani, Radadiya, & Vidani, 2016).

Reliability Test:

The reliability test conducted is Cronbach's alpha which gives value 0.902 which shows that data collected is highly reliable and consistent (Vidani, Chack, & Rathod, 2017) (Vidani, 2018). This suggest that the questionnaire formed was appropriate for the research (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018) (Vasveliyya & Vidani, 2019).

Hypothesis Testing:

Hypothesis testing was conducted using Chi- square approach to find the relationship between demographic characteristics and factors influencing the satisfaction level of the customer towards Allen Solly apparel (Sachaniya, Vora, & Vidani, 2019) (Vidani, 2019) (Vidani, Jacob, & Patel, 2019).

All nine hypotheses suggests that age does not influence satisfaction level because their p values are greater than 0.05 (Vidani J. N., 2020) (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020). It shows that a consumer's age has no impact on their level of satisfaction (Vidani & Das, 2021).

The rejection of the theories mentioned before, might be ascribed to a variety of internal and external factors (Vidani J. N., 2022) (Saxena & Vidani, 2023) (Vidani, Das, Meghrajani, & Singh, 2023). Though age is not a factor in any of these internal factors – such as their decision-making during purchases because many of them are of from age group of 18-24 years, variety of clothing and satisfaction from the apparels is important whereas, external factors include personal preference, brand loyalty, product availability, product variety, brand name, and many more (Vidani, Das, Meghrajani, & Chaudasi, 2023) (Bansal, Pophalkar, & Vidani, 2023) (Chaudhary, Patel, & Vidani, 2023).

Future Scope

Although this research was conducted only in Ahmedabad, it can be expanded to cover different areas in the future. It should be noted that the results of this study are based on a sample size of only 131, and a larger sample size would provide more accurate results. To gain a better understanding of consumer satisfaction levels and the factors that influence purchasing decisions, in-depth interviews can be conducted. Also, while this research used a quantitative research method, the data can also be collected using a qualitative research method.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The research concludes that non-branded apparel shoppers in Ahmedabad are a diverse group with different preference as they shop online from amazon. They are not solely driven by factors like price or brands but are prioritize by variety, styling, trends and product quality. This will also help retailers to come up with unique and diverse option in competitive prices with good product quality. This will open up opportunities for small scale retailers as they can promote their product on a wide scale and can get benefitted from it. Hence, this research will be

very productive for the new comers as well as established one. This data gives some valuable factors for Allen Solly to refine its strategies and provide more satisfying shopping experience to its customers in Ahmedabad.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of A Study on Customer Satisfaction Towards Allen Solly Apparels in order to improve this research and add insight to readers

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